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*THE GENESIS OF RESEARCH ON ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS IN
BRAZIL AND THE PUBLICATION IN FOREIGN JOURNALS¹*

**A GÊNESE DA PESQUISA EM ECOSSISTEMAS EMPREENDEDORES NO
BRASIL E A PUBLICAÇÃO EM PERIÓDICOS ESTRANGEIROS**

Fernando Antonio Prado Gimenez²

Research and publications on entrepreneurial ecosystems in Brazil are relatively recent. Over the past few years, I have searched various sources to determine the beginning of studies in this field in Brazil. In this editorial, I report the results of these searches and then comment on the presence of articles written by researchers from the country who have managed to overcome the barriers to publication in foreign journals.

My intention in this text is not very ambitious. Initially, I simply aim to document the pioneering Brazilian scientific production in this still very young field. I then present data on the dissemination of Brazilian production in foreign journals, using two approaches: articles accepted in the five highest-impact journals in the field of entrepreneurship and other articles published in additional foreign journals.

At the outset, I emphasize the limitations of my search procedures, which inevitably could not cover all possible reports of studies and/or research in the field. In these searches, I did not consider books, research reports, undergraduate or specialization theses, or papers presented at national and international events - except for events organized by the National Association of Graduate Programs in Administration (ANPAD) and the Meetings on Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management (EGEPE). I also did not

¹ DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19609520

² Universidade Federal do Paraná. gimenez@ufpr.br

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search for articles in journals published in languages other than Portuguese or English. Finally, when using Lattes CVs as a source of information on publications, it is possible that they did not contain complete data on each author's publications.

Nevertheless, I hope that this preliminary information on research into entrepreneurial ecosystems in Brazil will encourage more comprehensive studies, contributing to an expansion of our knowledge about the emergence and the evolving dynamics of Brazilian research in this field.

GENESIS OF RESEARCH ON ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS IN BRAZIL

Initially, based on a search of the Theses and Dissertations Database of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES)³, I identified one master's dissertation and one doctoral thesis that I consider to be the pioneering works on entrepreneurial ecosystems in the country. They were defended in 2014 and 2015, respectively.

Although the search revealed two additional theses containing the keyword "entrepreneurial ecosystems" - Lemos (2011) and Gomes (2013) - these did not address the topic in a broad sense, that is, as a set of organizations, institutions, and actors that interact interdependently, creating conditions conducive to the emergence of new ventures (Stam, 2015; Spigel, 2020). Lemos (2011) uses the concept of entrepreneurial ecosystem within universities, in a very narrow sense. Gomes (2013), in turn, addresses the topic with a focus on the management of entrepreneurial ecosystems by entrepreneurs and does not rely on a theoretical framework of entrepreneurial ecosystems.

In fact, the master's dissertation by Sheyla Fernandes (2014) was the first to use the broader concept of entrepreneurial ecosystem, linked to the notion

³ <https://catalogodeteses.capes.gov.br/catalogo-teses/#/>

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of the National System of Entrepreneurship proposed by Ács, Szerb, and Autio (2014). Similarly, the following year, the doctoral thesis by Meire Oliveira (2015) employed an expanded concept of entrepreneurial ecosystem, based on the dimensions proposed by Isenberg (2011): policies, financial resources, culture, support institutions, human capital, and markets.

Next, I conducted a search in the proceedings of the EGEPE conferences⁴, which have been held since 2000. Since 2012, EGEPE has been organized by the National Association of Studies in Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management (ANEGEPE) in partnership with universities and other organizations⁵.

At the 9th Meeting of Studies in Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management (IX EGEPE), held in 2016 at the University of Passo Fundo, the first two papers on the topic were presented: Inácio Júnior, Dionisio, Gimenez, and Morini (2016); and Lopes (2016). The first analyzed the Brazilian entrepreneurial ecosystem in light of the National System of Entrepreneurship theory (Ács, Szerb, and Autio, 2014). The second, although it did not reference prior research on entrepreneurial ecosystems, explored the entrepreneurial ecosystem in India, comparing it with other countries and pointing out the general conditions faced by Indian entrepreneurs in the economic and social context.

On the other hand, in the proceedings of events organized by ANPAD⁶, the earliest paper I found was presented at the 29th Symposium on Technological Innovation Management. Adopting the model proposed by Isenberg (2011), Santos and Zen (2016) investigated how the entrepreneurial ecosystem influences the development of businesses with innovative potential in Porto Digital, in Recife, the capital of Pernambuco.

⁴ <https://anegepe.org.br/anais-do-egepe/>

⁵ <https://anegepe.org.br/apresentacao-egepe/>

⁶ https://eventos.anpad.org.br/pt_br/article_search/

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Previously, when I conducted a survey of entrepreneurship articles published in Brazilian journals (Gimenez, 2017), I identified three articles addressing the topic: Carvalho, Viana, and Mantovani (2016); Inácio Júnior, Autio, Morini, Gimenez, and Dionisio (2016); and Mineiro, Miranda, Ottoboni, and Pasin (2016). These works were part of a research category I called “Environmental Determinants of Entrepreneurship,” which included 26 articles published between 1963 and 2016. Among these were the three articles focused on entrepreneurial ecosystems. The common link among these articles is that they reported the results of research on the social, economic, environmental, and political attributes of the context in which entrepreneurship occurs, as well as on innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystems as factors influencing the emergence of new ventures (Gimenez, 2017: 269–273).

Subsequently, in another literature review study focused exclusively on texts about entrepreneurial ecosystems, I identified 44 articles published between 2015 and 2023 (Gimenez, 2023). In this study, I also identified an article published in 2015 that is the earliest to address the topic in Brazilian journals (Souza, Gerhard, La Róvere, and Câmara, 2015). However, the authors merely used the expression without clarifying or conceptualizing what an entrepreneurial ecosystem is. There is also no citation of any previous work in the entrepreneurial ecosystem literature.

Thus, between 2015 and 2017, I identified five articles published in Brazilian journals. Then, between 2018 and 2020, 16 articles were identified, and between 2021 and 2023, another 23. A partial list of these texts can be found in Gimenez, Stefenon, and Inácio Júnior (2022).

In a quick search of the SPELL⁷ electronic library, using the terms “ecossistema empreendedor” or “entrepreneurial ecosystem” in article titles, I

⁷ <https://www.spell.org.br/>

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identified 13 more articles published between 2024 and 2025. In total, therefore, between 2015 and 2025, I identified 57 papers, approximately five per year.

Thus, it can be considered that the genesis of studies on entrepreneurial ecosystems in Brazil occurred in the mid-2010s. More specifically, starting in 2014 with a master's dissertation, followed by a doctoral thesis and a journal article in 2015. In 2016, in the wake of these works, three papers presented at national scientific events and three articles in Brazilian journals emerged. Chart 1 summarizes this information.

Chart 1 – Pioneering publications on entrepreneurial ecosystems in Brazil

Year	Type of publication	Title	Autorshi
2014	Master's dissertation	Avaliação de parques tecnológicos: uma proposta de modelo para parques de 3ª. Geração	S. C. R. Fernandes
2015	Doctoral thesis	Modelo para o estímulo à criação de spin-offs acadêmicas baseado em ecossistemas empreendedores	M. R. de Oliveira
	Journal article	Entrepreneurship and creation of new business: key factors of Brazilian entrepreneurial ecosystem.	L. L. F. de Souza, F. Gerhard, R. L. La Rovere e S. F. Câmara
2016	Paper scientific event	Ecossistemas de empreendedorismo e o estímulo à criação de negócios inovadores: o caso da indústria de aplicativos do Porto Digital	D. A. G. dos Santos e A. C. Zen
		Análise do ecossistema empreendedor do Brasil	E. Inácio Júnior, E. A. Dionisio, F. A. P. Gimenez e C. Morini
		Um olhar sobre o ecossistema empreendedor na Índia: comparativos internacionais e relações entre religiões, classes sociais e atividade empreendedora	R. Lopes
2016	Journal article	O papel da FAPESP no ecossistema empreendedor do estado de São Paulo	L. M. C. Carvalho, A. B. N. Viana e D. M. N. Mantovani
		Analysis of the Brazilian entrepreneurial ecosystem	E. Inácio Júnior, E. Autio, C. Morini, F. A. P. Gimenez e E. A. Dionisio,
		Investigação do potencial de um polo de inovação para a criação de uma rede de investidores anjos a partir de seu ecossistema empreendedor	A. C. Mineiro, B. P. Miranda, C. Ottononi e L. E. Pasin.

Source: Elaborated by author (2026)

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In this context of the relative youth of the topic within the Brazilian research community, in the next section I address the phenomenon of international publication of studies on entrepreneurial ecosystems produced by researchers affiliated with teaching and research institutions based in Brazil.

PUBLICATIONS IN FOREIGN ENGLISH-LANGUAGE PERIODICALS

In this section, I present the results of two searches I conducted using different procedures. First, following the procedure adopted by Foss, Henry, Ahl, and Mikalsen (2019), I focused on identifying articles published in the five highest-impact journals in entrepreneurship research: *Small Business Economics*; *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*; *Journal of Business Venturing*; *Journal of Small Business Management*; and *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*. In this search, considering that the topic has been addressed for just over a decade, I chose to examine only articles published between 2023 and 2025. At this stage, I found only three articles authored by Brazilian researchers.

In a second stage, I used a somewhat broader procedure, initially identifying researchers who had presented papers on entrepreneurial ecosystems at ENEGEPE conferences and at events promoted by ANPAD. This search resulted in the identification of 68 authors. I then examined the Lattes CVs of these researchers, searching for articles with the terms “ecossistema empreendedor” or “entrepreneurial ecosystem” in their titles that had been published in foreign journals. This effort led to the identification of an additional 29 articles published from 2017 onward, including four in 2026. Only 18 of the previously identified researchers were among the authors of these published articles.

In total, considering both searches, I identified 32 texts. When combined with the articles published in Brazil, this results in 89 publications over the period. Thus, approximately 35% of the articles were disseminated in foreign journals.

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Brazilian production in the highest-impact journals

Between 2023 and 2025, in the five highest-impact journals in the field of entrepreneurship, I identified 51 articles, of which, as mentioned above, only three included Brazilian co-authors.

Small Business Economics was the journal with the highest number of articles on entrepreneurial ecosystems (33). The other four journals published fewer articles in this research field: seven in Entrepreneurship & Regional Development; five in Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice; four in Journal of Small Business Management; and only two in Journal of Business Venturing.

The articles featuring Brazilian authors were published in 2025, with two appearing in Small Business Economics (Fischer, Guerrero, Mayer, Meissner, Schäfer, and Theodoraki, 2025; Pigola, Fischer, Moraes, Prado, and Ribeiro, 2025) and one in Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice (Santos, Fischer, Alves, and Roundy, 2025).

It can be observed that the articles published in the highest-impact journals in the field of entrepreneurship resulted from the collective effort of multiple authors, typically ranging from four to six contributors. Moreover, collaboration in the production of these articles involves authors from various institutions, both national and international, thus characterizing a multi-institutional and international network of cooperation.

Production published in other foreign journals

In addition to the three articles presented in the previous subsection, I identified 29 more texts published in foreign journals with the participation of Brazilian authors. The first publication I found is by Santos, Zen, and Schmidt (2017), who investigated, through a case study, how entrepreneurial ecosystems

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influence the development of businesses with innovative potential. The study adopted Isenberg's (2011) model as its theoretical basis for analysis.

In the following year, Silva, Anholon, Rampasso, Quelhas, Leal Filho, and Silva (2018) published the results of a study on the maturity of the Brazilian entrepreneurial ecosystem based on the opinions and perceptions of professionals affiliated with business incubators in the country.

I identified four additional texts in 2021, three in 2022, two in 2023, and four in 2024. In 2025, I found 10 more, totaling 13 when including the articles published in the highest-impact journals. Finally, by mid-April 2026, based on the researchers' Lattes CVs, four additional articles are reported.

Similarly to the articles published in the highest-impact journals, these papers were also the result of collective efforts involving between three and six authors. In terms of the diversity of research institutions involved, most articles included authors from at least two institutions, with only a few papers authored exclusively by researchers from a single institution.

Considering the total of 32 articles, they were published across 21 journals. There was also a balanced distribution between teams composed exclusively of Brazilian authors (17 articles) and those including at least one foreign co-author (15 articles). Chart 2 provides further details of this production.

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Chart 2 – Articles published in foreign journals with the participation of Brazilian researchers

Journal	Year	Authoship
Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice	2025	J. B. Santos, B. B. Fischer, A. C. Alves e P. T. Roundy
Foresight and STI Governance	2025	D. B. Vicentin, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, N. B. do Prado, B. B. Fischer, B. S. C. Campello e R. Anholon
Growth and Change	2026	A. Pigola, B. B. Fischer e G. H. S. M. de Moraes
International Journal of Business Innovation and Research	2018	M. C. Silva, R. Anholon, I. S. Rampasso, O. L. G. Quelhas, W. Leal Filho e D. Silva
International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research	2026	D. B. Vicentin, A. Pigola, B. Fischer e G. H. S. M. de Moraes
International Journal of Technological Learning, Innovation and Development	2022	B. Fischer, A. Bayona-Alsina, A. K. L. da Rocha e G. H. S. M. de Moraes
Journal of Business Venturing Insights	2024	S. Schäfer, B. Fischer, P. R. Schaeffer e A. Balestrin
	2025	P. H. Napoli, B. B. Fischer e G. H. S. M. Moraes N. V. Noak, B. Fischer e P. T. Roundy,
Journal of Business Research	2021	P. R. Schaeffer, M. Guerrero e B. B. Fischer
	2022	B. Fischer, D. Meissner, N. Vonortas e M. Guerrero
Journal of Cleaner Production	2024	D. C. Vicentin, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, B. B. Fischer, B. S. C. Campello, N. B. do Prado e R. Anholon
Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies	2024	F. Ribeiro, C. B. S. Cirani, E. Scornavacca e V. R. S. Pires
	2025	E. Inacio Júnior, E. A. Dionisio e F. A. P. Gimenez
Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy	2025	R. D. B. Jaeger, M. K. Mendes, C. Schutte e A. C. Zen
		N. B. D. Prado, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, B. B. Fischer e R. Anholon
Journal of Intellectual Capital	2021	E. Inacio Junior, E. A. Dionisio, B. B. Fischer, Y. Li e D. Meissner
	2025	D. C. Vicentin, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, B. Fischer, N. B. Prado, D. Meissner e R. Anholon
Journal of Research in Business, Economics and Management	2017	D. A. G. dos Santos, A. C. Zen e V. K. Schmidt
Small Business Economics	2025	B. Fischer, M. Guerrero, H. Mayer, D. Meissner, S. Schäfer e C. Theodoraki
		A. Pigola, B. Fischer, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, N. B. do Prado e J. de A. Ribeiro
Sustainability	2024	A. Pigola, B. Fischer e G. H. S. M. de Moraes

(continues)

Chart 2 – Articles published in foreign journals with the participation of Brazilian researchers (continuation)

Journal	Year	Authoship
Sustainable Development	2025	M. A. de Moraes, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, N. B. do Prado e B. B. Fischer
		G. C. Pelegrini, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, N. B. do Prado, B. B. Fischer e R. Anholon
The Annals of Regional Science	2021	A. C. Alves, B. B. Fischer e N. S. Vonortas
Technological Forecasting and Social Change	2021	E. A. Dionisio, E. Inácio Júnior e B. B. Fischer
Technology in Society	2022	G. G. Reis, E. G. Villar, F. A. P. Gimenez, C. F. M. Molento e P. Ferri
Technovation	2023	J. B. Santos, A. R. Fernandes, P. T. de Oliveira, L. M. Maia e R. B. Partyka
		E. H. S. Siqueira, B. B. Fischer, A. Bin e J. Kickul
The Journal of Technology Transfer	2025	A. Pigola, B. Fischer, D. B. Audretsch e G. H. S. M. de Moraes
	2026	B. B. Fischer, A. C. Alves, N. S. Vonortas e R. Brown
		P. H. Napoli, B. B. Fischer, G. H. S. M. de Moraes, N. Vonortas e A. Bailey

Source: Elaborated by author (2026)

In sum, it can be observed that the presence of articles on entrepreneurial ecosystems in English-language journals has grown in recent years. This growth may be the result of increased interaction among researchers from various national and international institutions. In other words, the presence of Brazilian research in foreign English-language journals reflects an effort to build research networks at both the national and international levels. Notably, there was not a single case of an article published by a single author.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In concluding this editorial, I observe that the effort to publish research findings by the Brazilian academic community is highly concentrated in a small number of universities. The Universidade Estadual de Campinas stands out as the institution with the strongest presence, with authors involved in 28

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publications, particularly the group led by Professor Bruno Fischer, as well as, to a lesser extent, members of other research groups from the same university.

Other teaching and research institutions with affiliated authors include: the São Paulo School of Business Administration (3 articles); the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (3); the Federal University of Paraná (2); and the Regional University of Blumenau Foundation, the Federal University of Espírito Santo, the Federal Fluminense University, and the Nove de Julho University, each with one article. In other words, researchers from only eight Brazilian universities - most of them public institutions, either state or federal - have overcome the barriers to publishing on entrepreneurial ecosystems in foreign journals.

A second point worth highlighting concerns access to the highest-impact journals. In the sample of articles I identified, Brazilian studies were present in only two of the five top journals. This fact calls for reflection within the research community: what might be causing this limited presence?

Certainly, there is an expectation of greater originality and contribution to the field to publish in such journals. Are we capable of producing this type of research? Or do we face difficulties and barriers specific to our context? On this matter, Nassif (2019, p. i), in an editorial for REGEPE Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management, noted that “it is necessary to mention the difficulty in producing high-quality scientific articles, arising from the numerous problems that we, Brazilian researchers, face.” It would be worthwhile examining this issue more systematically, perhaps by comparing successful and unsuccessful experiences. In the analysis of the publications I identified, there seems to be at least a partial explanation: publishing abroad requires collective effort. But what else? This is a question for future research.

Finally, I invite the community of researchers in the field of entrepreneurial ecosystems in Brazil to seek further information on the evolution

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of this topic within Brazilian academia. Of particular relevance would be the undertaking of a systematic review of these publications, both in Brazil and abroad, in order to reveal our contribution to this highly dynamic field at the international level.

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